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PHOENIX

Nanomedicine for organ transplant tolerance

D5.1 Project Website

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PROJECT WEBSITE

Contents

1. Executive Summary.....	4
2. Introduction and Background.....	4
3. Approach.....	5
3.1 Logo and Branding.....	6
3.2 Website.....	7
3.2.1 Technology.....	8
3.2.2 Website updates.....	8
3.2.3 Analytics.....	8
3.2.4 Privacy Policy.....	8
3.3 Social Media.....	9
4. Results.....	10
4.1 Web Logo and Branding - Design Decisions.....	10
4.2 PHOENIX Homepage.....	11
4.3 What is PHOENIX? page.....	12
4.4 Team Profiles.....	12
4.5 Other pages: Publications, Related Projects, Media and Materials and News.....	13
5. Impact and Conclusion.....	13

1. Executive Summary

Work package 5 (WP5) - *Communications, Dissemination, Exploitation and Management* in the PHOENIX project has four objectives:

1. To orchestrate and facilitate the progress of the project and all WPs and activities
2. To promote the aims and activities of the project (communication) and of its results (dissemination)
3. To identify, manage and protect new intellectual property and innovation
4. To prepare for the further development and exploitation of the project results.

The topic of this report, Deliverable 5.1 - Project Website (D5.1) is an output of Task 5.2, an ongoing task focussed on communication activities throughout the project.

In PHOENIX, communication activities will focus on presenting the project itself and sharing updates throughout the three years of the project. Target audiences for communications include the following key stakeholders: scientists, clinicians, patients, healthcare providers, industry; and the public. In Task 5.2, in addition to providing general public information, communication will also target other audiences such as transplant patients and carers, academic and industrial research communities, transplant clinicians, and industry sectors that could play a role in commercialisation and exploitation of the project outcomes. Further, the project website creates a channel through which dissemination (T5.3), namely awareness of the results and outcomes of the project during and after the project will be raised.

One key step in communicating the project and enabling the dissemination of results is establishing and maintaining the **project website** (<https://www.phoenix-he.eu/>) which was live effective on 18 May 2023. The website includes descriptions of the project concept, the team involved, and will include results achieved, key innovations, benefits for patients, hospitals and other stakeholders, and societal impact (to be updated throughout the project). The [project website](#) is also a key channel, linked to social media, through which contact with the project and its partners can be made.

2. Introduction and Background

Organ transplant medicine is currently limited by life-long immunosuppression and vulnerability to infections, malignancies and cardiovascular diseases. Further there is a 20% rate of long-term graft failure. The PHOENIX project addresses this challenge, by reprogramming the local immune micro-environment around a graft organ, inducing long-term transplant tolerance without broader systemic immunosuppression.

In PHOENIX, the team are designing and building a unique nanomedicine which delivers ubiquitous or self-antigens - common to all humans – that will redirect the host immune response against the graft toward regulation and tolerance development. These medicines will be demonstrated in murine and porcine models, laying the foundation for human clinical trials immediately post-project.

WP5 has four main objectives, as outlined above, with the second objective (*to promote the aims and activities of the project (communication) and of its results (dissemination)*) being relevant to this deliverable report (D5.1). WP5 cuts across all other work packages in the project and is central via its

coordination, project management, communication, dissemination and exploitation functions, to the overall success of the project.

D5.1, the PHOENIX Project website, was live effective on 18 May 2023 at <https://www.phoenix-he.eu>. This report presents an overview of the approach to the project website development, including the web design process and results, being the website itself, that have been carried out under Task 5.2.

The PHOENIX website (Figure 1) is essential for communicating the project mission and results.

Figure 1 PHOENIX Website Homepage

The PHOENIX target audiences include:

- the general public
- the medical community, including patients, carers and researchers
- industry
- key opinion leaders.

A project website is key to building a community of followers. By documenting our project story and engaging with our target audiences through the website (and related social media), we will publicly establish PHOENIX as a leader in the transplant medicine domain, as PHOENIX addresses the global challenge of transplant graft survival. Although transplantation success rates have improved in recent years, life-long immunosuppression is required to prevent graft rejection. This comes with a risk of cancer, infections, and other complications, placing clinicians in the dilemma to balance the risk of rejection and graft loss with the risk of progression of infection and cancer.

The PHOENIX website will enable communication about, create interest in, and demand for, our research outputs within the medical and research and development communities. This in turn supports exploitation planning (Task 5.5), given this consortium of clinician scientists is determined to deliver the technology underpinned by PHOENIX into the clinic as soon as possible.

3. Approach

The core activities and considerations related to the conceptualisation and development of the website are described below.

3.1 Logo and Branding

Five different logos were developed by Pintail for project partner consideration, see Figure 2.

Figure 2 PHOENIX Potential Logos

Partners were unanimous in their voting (in Month 1) for the first logo presented (Figure 3 below). This logo depicts a modern, sleek phoenix in gold, grey and black, with tail feathers merging into a geometric circle, symbolising unity, and collaboration. This logo reflects the transformative impact on patients’ lives and organ transplantation as a whole.

Figure 3 Partners agreed on the PHOENIX logo

From this, the colour palette was assembled, as shown in Figure 4 below. The logo dictates the project website's 'look and feel' and the colour scheme will be reflected in other associated materials. Slides, posters and other 'branding' materials when created in collaboration with all partners will be made available for download on the website.

Figure 4 PHOENIX colour palette for promotional materials and the website

3.2 Website

The project website was developed during April 2023. The initial website includes:

- Project information (mission, concept, research background information)
- A news feed that will be updated regularly and translates scientific content, so it is accessible to a range of audiences, from researchers to the general public
- Media and materials
- Partner profiles and links
- Contact information
- EU Emblem and Statement
- Links to Twitter and LinkedIn
- Privacy policy

Content published on the website is overall, tailored for the general public. The website and social media communication will be simple, relevant, and factual. Technical and often complex scientific information is translated into a language that is simple to understand, reinforced with evidence, and illustrated with supporting media and images. In addition, promotional newsletters will be created and shared to support the PHOENIX goals. Additional pages will be developed as the dissemination and exploitation activities progress, targeting our specialist audiences (clinicians, partners, other projects, and potential collaborators). Essentially, we will tailor content to suit different audiences, whilst ensuring that our core message remains constant.

Due diligence will be carried out before the publication of resources online (web pages, news items, social media) to ensure that intellectual property (IP) and potential publications are protected.

3.2.1 Technology

The project website uses the WordPress content management system (CMS). Nearly one-third of websites use this powerful platform,¹ which has enabled us to build a project-specific theme, implement good search engine optimization (SEO), and build a site that works on a multitude of platforms and devices (across multiple browsers and on devices such as desktops and mobiles). WordPress is an industry standard and is easy to use, meaning that new pages, news posts, and other media can be shared rapidly, all the while conforming to the project theme and working responsively. Regular and automatic back-ups of the site and associated database ensure that the site has good fault tolerance and availability and can roll back where necessary.

The site is hosted by Anu hosting services on the cloud.² Anu is a well-trusted and mature internet-service provider. They guarantee good availability, ensuring minimal downtime. The EU domain name phoenix-he.eu was registered to give us a European identity and signifies that this is a cross-border project connected with the European Union.

3.2.2 Website updates

Design, development, and maintenance of the project website is the main responsibility of Pintail (PT). The team at PT have significant experience with web development, with a particular focus on designing and maintaining sites for European-funded research projects. PT will update the website content regularly throughout the project's lifetime, with all partners featuring and contributing content. To ensure that it reflects the current project status, the website will be reviewed at each General Assembly meeting. Partners are also encouraged to send project news, as and when they become available. In addition, bi-weekly 'calls for news' from partners are made in conjunction with our internal reporting schedule.

3.2.3 Analytics

Google Analytics³ will enable us to monitor and track our visitors. This important tool enables us to assess the impact of news articles, and the number of visitors to the site, their locations, and the platforms they are on. Understanding our visitors, their behaviours, and where they come from means that we can understand the extent to which our online communication is effective. Google Analytics, in particular, provides a simple toolkit for customising reports, is free, carries out automated data collection for the site, and has extensive documentation.

3.2.4 Privacy Policy

The website includes a Privacy Policy as required, providing information about:

- Who we are
- What personal data we collect and why we collect it
- What data is collected when you are on the site (including analytics and cookies)
- Who we share your data with
- How long we retain your data

¹ <https://wordpress.com/>

² <https://www.anu.net/>

³ <https://analytics.google.com>

- Additional information about links to Youtube and Twitter
- Ability for the user to not accept any third-party content

3.3 Social Media

To date, two PHOENIX social accounts have been established, we will continue to build an audience through social media. These accounts are used to communicate the project message, and activity will be tracked and reported upon in our interim and final reporting. Herein, we share our news, videos and photos from our partners and use all opportunities to drive traffic to the project website.

Twitter ([@Phoenix_Nano](https://twitter.com/Phoenix_Nano)) (Figure 5) has been a focus in the project's first months. On Twitter, more diverse content is posted more frequently with related content from partners re-shared and dissemination materials such as PHOENIX press releases and publications posted.

Figure 5: PHOENIX Twitter pages, branded with Project logo and EU acknowledgement

LinkedIn has also been set up (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12830914/>) and will target professionals in its content, including researchers and potential industry collaborators.

Figure 6: PHOENIX LinkedIn Public Group

Facebook and Instagram will be used further into the project (when more activities have occurred) to educate, inform, and connect with patient organizations, creating opportunities for two-way dialogue. YouTube will also be used via embedding videos as they become available into the project website.

4. Results

The following section provides a visual exploration of the main elements of the project website, full access is available via the live website at www.phoenix-he.eu.

4.1 Web Logo and Branding - Design Decisions

Logo and colour palette: The PHOENIX logo features at the top-centre of each page. The colour scheme used on the Homepage splash image (Figure 7) and throughout the site draws from the project logo (Figure 3, above).

Header: A site menu is held in the header and is consistent across all pages. Links to our social media profiles are also present (Figure 7).

Footer: Horizon Europe acknowledgements and project information are contained in the footer alongside recent news items and recent tweets. The footer is consistent across all pages (Figure 8).

Figure 7 PHOENIX Logo at top of each page

Figure 8 PHOENIX footer

4.2 PHOENIX Homepage

The PHOENIX Homepage (Figures 1, 9) briefly introduces the project mission in plain English.

Figure 9 PHOENIX Homepage

4.3 What is PHOENIX? page

The *What is PHOENIX* page (Figure 19, <https://www.phoenix-he.eu/what-is-phoenix/>) includes short descriptions of the key concepts related to why the project is needed, what novel technologies and knowledge the project offers to the transplant community, and the benefits this research will bring. It also describes the research end goals and what can be expected after the project concludes.

Figure 10 About PHOENIX

4.4 Team Profiles

Individual PHOENIX partner profiles (Figure 11) are included describing the partner organisations and groups involved in the project and their roles.

Figure 11 Team entry for Mario Negri

4.5 Other pages: Publications, Related Projects, Media and Materials and News

In terms of Open Science, PHOENIX will prioritise the early and open sharing of project outputs, including publications, data, experimental methods, know-how and workflows. On the website, pages and additional, new pages will be added and populated as such content becomes available. The website will grow further based on the developments of the project. This source of materials will support Task 5.3 – dissemination of the project.

The first news item included is the Press Release to launch the project, as shown in Figure 12 or readable via this [link](#).

Figure 12 Press Release to launch the project

5. Impact and Conclusion

To summarize, the PHOENIX project website is tailored for general audiences, as well as the medical community and key opinion leaders. The website will be promoted through social media channels and during events where partners present the project mission and results. This adaptable resource will grow over the lifetime of the project, delivering clear and relevant project-related information to citizens and specialist audiences.